

Internal Assessment in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State: Implications for the Teacher Counsellor

Miwari, Goodluck U. (PhD) & Eleberi, Bright U. (PhD) & Umukoro, Coral (PhD)

Department of Educational Foundations
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt

Corresponding Authors' E-mail: goodluck.miwari@ust.edu.ng¹,
eleberibright@yahoo.com² & coralpatron31@gmail.com³

Abstract

Amongst the responsibilities of the teacher as a stakeholder at all levels of education is the proper assessments of his clients to enable him give accurate feedback to the public. Assessment and in fact the internal type is viewed very seriously by providers of education including government. In the secondary school, assessment is carried out in different ways by different personnel but the question is how do these personnel with different skills applied aggregate the result to have the accurate feedback desired. This paper discusses the preparation, administration and control of internal assessment in secondary schools and the implication for the teacher. Even with a test prepared by a test expert, in the hand of an unscrupulous or the well-meaning but uninformed user, a test can hazardous. Therefore, advancing the procedures and technicalities of preparation and administration of internal assessment in such a way that confounding variables will be minimized if not totally checked, this paper laid emphasis on its control to achieve the much-desired quality assurance and quality control (QA QC). Consequently, suggestions were made which includes basic training for intending teachers, mandatory in-service training and/or workshop exclusively to groom teachers on testing and measurement, and the establishment of examination committees in school, whose membership must have requisite knowledge of testing.

Keywords: Administration, Control, Internal Assessment, Trained Teacher, Untrained Teacher.

INTRODUCTION

Assessment of scholars and students had been an old-time practice in education. From time to time, on weekly, termly or yearly bases, teachers assess their students basically, through written and oral test and observational technique. Somehow, assessment had been a continuous process of some sort, but the records were not applied cumulatively and final grading of student were not based on cumulative scores as it is operational today, in accordance with the prescriptions of the Federal Ministry of Education (FME 1985), in the National Policy on Education of 1981.

Federal Ministry of Education (FME 1985) according to Enyi (2006) prescribed a mechanism whereby the final grading of a student in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains of behaviour takes into account in a systematic way all his performances, during a given period of schooling. The distinguishing feature of these types of assessment is its characteristics of being systematic and comprehensive, and the cumulative feature which is accounted for. This conforms to Gbamanja's position that assessment should be a continuous updating of the teachers' judgment about his own pupils, which should permit a cumulative judgment about his own pupil's performance to be made, (Gbamanja, 2001). For the purpose of this paper, however, assessment and its process will be looked at as a concept on its own, as a means to evaluation and not as part of evaluation.

What is Assessment

Asuru (2016) defined assessment as a process of organizing measurement data and fashioning them in an interpretable manner. He went further to buttress that assessment describe the worth of pupil's behaviour but fails to pass judgment. Going by this position then assessment has to do with the classification and grouping of measurement, and it involves the analysis of data so that their worth or quality is easily comprehended. Measurements are quantitative facts associated with events. Measurements and data are synonymous, when measurement is viewed as a noun.

Assessment is essential for improving the quality of education and learning (Black & William, 2009). If assessment has a formative purpose, it is used to support student learning. Formative assessment has the potential to enhance student achievement (Bennett, 2011; Black & William, 2009). According to Gbamanja

(2001), assessment is used as a term for investigating the status of an individual or group with references to certain expected outcomes. Measurement is a scale that measures quantitatively but assessment is the status of the individual or groups using the scale. The implication of Gbamanja's view is that assessment interprets measurement. It tells how well an individual or group of individuals have achieved in a particular concept, skills or course of study, using various forms of measuring techniques. Assessment therefore from the foregoing, is the process of classifying and analyzing of data or measurements so as to show comparisons and differences in groups or classes. Data or measurements are facts gathered through written test and/or observation. Assessment analyzes and classifies the data and lends itself to value judgment or evaluation.

Testing, measurement and assessment are most often used interchangeably. Of course they are hardly separable as they are complementarily applied for adequate understanding. Testing is simply the administration of instrument on an individual or group in order to elicit characteristics or underlying traits in the individuals. On the one hand, measurement when used as a verb is synonymous with testing as both are processes of determining quantitatively, the characteristics of a phenomenon. Measurement as seen by Asuru (2016) is the systematic process of quantifying the characteristics of an object or the assignment of numbers to events according to acceptable rules. Conversely, measurement as a noun is an item of fact or a datum (data for plural) obtained by following a given rule to assign numbers to events. The entire process of developing and administering an instrument on individuals (testing), determining or quantifying of characteristics or underlying traits (measurement) and the classification and analysis of measurement data (assessment) are collectively seen as assessment in the educative process and it is in this sense that assessment is treated in this paper.

Consequently, assessment may be defined as the mechanism by which individual characteristics or underlying traits are elicited or determined and quantified, classified and analyzed in an interpretable fashion to permit value judgment.

Types of Assessment

Assessment as it relates to the educational setting can be internal or external.

- (i) **Internal Assessment:** At the secondary school level, internal assessment refers to the assessment restricted to and carried out solely by staff of a particular school. The designing of the assessment instrument, the administration, the scoring, and the analyses are all the responsibility of the staff of the given school. Expectedly therefore, internal assessment would vary to the extent that school's administration varies. Typical of internal assessment in secondary schools are class works, weekly test, terminal examinations and yearly promotion examinations. In this discourse therefore, internal assessment is defined as the use of instruments (e.g., a test or homework assignment) and processes (e.g., asking questions and classroom conversations) for gathering evidence about student learning (Van der Kleij, Vermeulen, Schildkamp, & Eggen, 2015; Stobart, 2008).
- (ii) **External Assessment:** External assessment as distinguished from the internal assessment comes from external bodies that may have been established by law and commissioned by the school, government or the sponsor of a program. Such assessment is done on all schools of the same level at the same time. There is no variability and the instrument is based on a common and uniform standard.

Examples of external assessment in Nigeria are the West African School Certificate Examination (WASCE), the Unified Tertiary Institutions Matriculation Examination (UTME), the various States and Federal Basic Education Certificate Examinations (BECE), the senior school certificate examinations (SSCE) and the National Technical Education Examination.

Assessment can be interpersonal which is a comparison of two person's performances on the same subject or test to determine the person with the higher achievement. It can also be intra-personal assessment which gives the level of progress of one individual in different tests at different time. e.g. the comparison of Oye's performance in mathematics in two or three different tests of equal or near equal difficulty.

Purpose of Assessment

That most or all the student in class failed in an examination would be frustrating to the teacher. A number of biases could be raised. The teacher may have failed in his method and has not communicated effectively. Little may be said about student background since it varies with the student and in particular, the class is seen as homogenous. The teacher needs to re-examine his teaching method to see where improvement could be made. The teacher's professional growth or lack of it will be judged based on the students' performance, in his willingness to change in his working relationship with children and in his overall efficiency as a teacher (Blair, Jones and Simpson 1975). Thus assessment helps the teacher to understand his professional position. He

evaluates himself through the students' performance as well as determines the level of achievement by pupils. To provide vocational guidance to clients the guidance counsellor needs to assess the clients. This ensures that children are enrolled into the series of courses in which they have interest and aptitude and which previous achievement indicates that they are most likely to succeed (Okoro 2006). In this respect, assessment is for guidance and counselling purposes. Assessment also builds confidence in students and hence discourages and reduces examination malpractice (cheating). When the result of assessment is made public to the student, he realizes his weaknesses and works on them while building and maintaining his strong position against external assessment.

Assessment Instruments

Broadly speaking, there are two categories of assessment instrument- the cognitive assessment instrument which is the usual test administered to student and the non- cognitive assessment instrument used mainly to determine affective and psychomotor traits, (Asuru 2006). Example includes questionnaire, rating scale, check list, sociometry, interview etc. the feedback given at the secondary schools to parents, guidance and sponsors encompasses both cognitive and non-cognitive assessment.

Mechanisms for Internal Assessment

(i) Preparation of Assessment Instrument

Like every other field of endeavour, the preparation of assessment instrument has its own techniques and methods. There are the general principles and there are the specific principles alienated to types. The use and the desired trait determine the type of instrument that will be applicable. For a proper and unbiased assessment of students, a secondary school teacher must prepare a suitable, valid and, reliable instrument and this call for adequate understanding of the construction techniques.

Asuru (2016), Okoro (2006) and Ubulom (2007) agreed that the preparation of assessment instrument involve four stages viz, planning, item writing, item analysis and marking scheme development stage. Okoro (2006) had also advanced some factors worth following in test preparation. A religious consideration of the factors and principles would have gone through the four stages itemized above. Therefore, to prepare a valid and reliable assessment instrument the teacher must bring those factors and principles to bear.

(ii) Theories of Learning

Education aims to promote learning. Assessment reveals deficiencies in learning rate and even teaching methods. A teacher can only effectively assess his student if he has some knowledge of the theories of learning. This knowledge of students learning abilities and inabilities will equip him to prepare assessment instrument that will reinforce and encourage learning.

(iii) Knowledge of Educational Objectives

All assessment is geared towards finding out the level of achievement of course objectives. The referenced authorities above posited that the various domains of educational objectives as they relate to cognitive learning by Bloom (1956), affective learning by Krathworl (1964) and psychomotor learning by Simpson (1966) must be borne in mind. Items must be devised for testing students' attainment of all three objectives as they deal with what students know, feel and can do. A very salient consideration is the complexity of learning being tested particularly with regard to the cognitive domains. Questions must be spread in such a way that most or all the levels of cognitive objectives are covered. Questions must require not mere recall of facts but comprehension, application, analysis and synthesis. This then calls for the knowledge of test blue print or table of specification which is a two dimensional grid specifying content and objective. When the cells of the blue prints are adequately covered, the content area and the various levels of objectives would have been taken care of.

(iv) Reference Point for Evaluation

Another very important factor worth considering while preparing assessment instrument is the reference point for evaluation after assessment. This could either be norm reference or criterion reference. Norm reference relates to discriminatory analysis of students' performances whereby the achievement of one student is compared to the other. Criterion reference on the other hand has to do with determining whether the student has achieved based on predetermined standard. This is interpersonal and intrapersonal assessment, respectively. Questions must be drawn from a common and uniform source (scheme or syllabus) and from same homogenous group.

The following principles should also be borne in mind and adhered to in preparing assessment materials. Ensure that items relate and cover the content adequately. For cognitive assessment examinees feel cheated

and discourage when items are concentrated on some and in fact small portion of the content. Coverage should be in content and level of objectives. It is advocated that in multiple choice items, some questions should test the attainment of affective objective and questions should not be intended to trick respondents. Wording should be very clear and understandable while instruction on what respondents should and should not do must be clearly given.

(v) Administration of Assessment Instrument

Congruent in sensitivity to preparation of assessment instrument is the administration. An improperly administered test limits or even impairs the generalizability of test result and this frustrates the basic rationale of testing. As many as are type of test are also specific procedures of administration but this paper concentrates on the common rationale of test administration. Anastasi and Urbina (2006) classified these into three phases-advanced orientations of the examiners, testing environment and testing condition.

Examiners and proctors need to get acquainted with the exam conditions. Familiarity with the instructions prevents misreading, hesitations and permit a more natural, informal manner during test administration. Materials should be placed within reach of the examiners without distraction. When complex apparatus are employed as in the case of performance test, frequent periodic checking and recalibration may be necessary. In a normal classroom most teachers are fond of just writing several questions on the board for students to respond to. This should be discouraged and even if this is to be accepted, teachers should ensure that questions are valid and are capable of yielding the desired characteristics. In some schools, questions are usually typed and is not done by the teacher or proctor himself, therefore adequate measures must be taken to prevent leakages through typist, and the production must be done as close to examination date as practicable Okoro (2006).

Testing environment and conditions have some level of influence on test scores. If testing is to be done in a usual classroom or place of study, not much may be required. However, if it is to be done in another room or hall, some measures of preparation could be necessary. Test environment should be well ventilated, free from noise and undue attractions, with adequate lightening. Both proctors and examinees should have adequate and spacious sitting facilities and walking spaces. The authors had a very frustrating experience when a test was administered to a particular school in Port Harcourt. Each of the JSS3classes had over 100 students with a seating ratio of between 4-5 students per desk of just 100 cm long. This should not be in an exam situation. Testing should be done during the morning and evening hours when temperature is not too harsh and examinees are more relaxed and capable of more concentration (Okoro 2006). Invigilators should be well brief and be informed in advance of their roles and responsibilities in as much as the subject or class teacher should not be allowed to invigilate his class or subject to avoid biases. Asuru (2006) had also advocated the provision of first aid materials as well as avoidance of sporadic announcement during administration of assessment. The value of this cannot be overemphasized.

(vi) Control of Internal Assessment

Even with a standardized test, in the hands of either unscrupulous or the well-meaning but uninformed user, a test can cause damage (Anastasi & Urbina, 2006). The principal reason for the control of internal assessment is to ensure that it is not invalidated. Invalidation could be of the instrument itself, or the result or scores. Whichever it is, with reasonable measure of control, invalidation could be checked. The whole idea about preparation and administration discussed earlier is aimed at preventing and controlling invalidation.

A distinction needs to be made between when a teacher gives special practice in problem closely resembling those expected in an examination and the usual procedure for preparing for school examination. In an internal assessment class and subject teachers should be interchanged for purposes of invigilation to ensure that class and subject teachers are not tempted to influence the performance of their students in an attempt to give instruction or explain concepts. It is common knowledge that examination malpractices are not restricted to external examination only. In fact, it is termed cheating when it has to do with the internal system (Okoro, 2006). The issue then is who is cheating and is cheating who? Is it the testee that is cheating the tester and to gain what and to whose expense? Examination malpractices whatever the form, has the same purpose viz: to obtain scores that the candidate does not merit and therefore invalidate test scores. These must be checked using appropriate measures. For instance, as a measure to make students build confidence in themselves and discourage some forms of examination malpractices in junior school certificate, the Rivers State Ministry of Education sometimes introduced an open-test items where a pool was exposed to students for practice prior to their actual exam. Whether psychometric properties are established for such test bank or not is a fact to be established. But the bottom line is that. training student with the standard of questions they expect helps them to build self confidence in themselves.

Control of internal assessment therefore is matters of efforts aimed at checking these examination malpractices as well as ensure adequate and accurate scoring and interpretation of test scores. For quick administration, scoring and interpretation, Okoro (2006) had advocated objective multiple choice test rather than essay items in internal assessment. Quick administration, scoring and interpretations is a measure of control as justice delayed, it is said is justice denied. This will reduce the incidence of students taking advantage to visit scorers and lobby for scores. Due to difficulties in developing objective items, a test bank can be established so that each time assessment is to be done, a ready set of questions or parallel ones are easily obtained.

Identification numbers should be written on all copies of the question papers and should be collected back for reuse in subsequent times. Adequate and clear instruction must be given at the beginning of the test and it is advisable to write all the instructions on the question paper. Grade all answer papers and destroy them after recording scores. Question papers must be preserved in safe places not accessible to everyone. A time frame within which marking and scoring must be accomplished should be given, and the school assessment officers must ensure that all instructions are adhered to. The issue of control as it affects confidentiality of result has been emphasized by expert as a matter of principles. The underlying principle is that an individual assessment records should not be released to a third person without the consent of the test taker, except such release is mandated by law or is permitted by law for valid purposes. Assessment records in the school are known to be longitudinal and are valuable for understanding and counselling the individual. Much as these records are kept, care must be taken in their use over time so as to avoid misuse as incorrect inferences from obsolete data. To prevent misuse, where records are retained either for legitimate longitudinal use in the interest of the individual or for acceptable research purpose, access to them should be subject to unusually stringent control (Anatasi and Urbina, 2006) emphasized.

(vii) Implication for the Teacher

A teacher is one who ensures that a child is equipped in so far as possible with the skills and knowledge that will enable him cope with his responsibilities as an adult in a complex world (Ojo, 1980). He is charged with the primary responsibility of teaching and imparting societal desirable qualities and skills to children. The teacher is the chief interpreter of the curriculum. The above definition presupposes the clear cut distinction that was made sometimes of auxiliary and trained teachers. According to Gbamaja (1997) auxiliary teachers include person without any teacher qualification. Thus, irrespective of one's qualification or specialization in any field if he/she has not undergone a pedagogical training, then he/she is an auxiliary teacher. A trained teacher on the other hand is an educationist who underwent pedagogical training including a good knowledge of the principles and practice of education, in addition to his teaching discipline. This is the view of Obagah (2000) when he said all the offerings one got through one's college, or universities that encompassed the educational and pedagogical components are what one needs to be certificated as a teacher.

Every teacher must have something to give out. It is often said and experience has proven that you can only teach what you know. Therefore, to succeed in this task of teaching the teacher must undergo some training and acquire some desired skill. According to Blair, Jones and Simpson (1975), a teacher's professional growth or lack of it will be reflected in his methods, in his willingness to change, in his working relationship with his children, and in his overall efficiency as a teacher. This is only possible through a pedagogical training. Having acquired the skills, the teacher still needs to understand the individual he is dealing with, the various and best approaches to dealing with him and all other techniques that are required for the overall achievement of the aims of teaching. This calls for a further training of the person who wants to teach. No wonder government in various countries emphasize on teacher education and teacher training certificate.

A trained teacher is one who has undergone a course of study especially designed to equip him with understanding human psychology, as well as the principles and practice of education. A trained teacher therefore has a skill to give and also has the skill on how to give out. He is trained to train others. He has the skill to find out if the beneficiary (apprentice, intern, etc.) is progressing in the studies or not, a major implication of internal assessment.

The untrained teacher on the other hand, is halfway of the trained. He must be teaching awl has what to teach but he does not understand who he is teaching, does not understand how he is teaching, and may not even understand when to teach. An untrained teacher might thus have the skills, the knowledge and the facts to give but does not have the skills and techniques of giving. To him teaching is frustrating because even to discover the level of followership of students will be difficult with the resultant effect of low progress rate of his students. Assessment to the untrained teacher is tricking the students. No wonder Gbamanja (1997) averred thus:

*A non-teacher cheats.
A poor teacher tells
An average or machine teacher informs
A good teacher teaches
An excellent teacher inspires*

From the foregoing, what implication then for the teacher in the preparation, administration and control of internal assessment in secondary schools.

To effectively support teachers in using internal assessment will first need to formulate the criteria characterizing a teacher who uses internal assessment effectively. What is such a teacher precisely doing in the classroom, which actions does he take, and which decisions does he make when, and why? If this is known, it can be determined which knowledge and skills internal assessment requires, and next, how teachers can acquire these best. In other words, given the complexity of the advocated assessment strategies, it is not surprising that teachers do not yet use much of them in our classrooms. Developing and implementing these strategies in school practice presupposes in-depth analysis, instructional design and training work.

Even currently, most teachers in the secondary school system are facing challenges in the implementation of internal assessment. Teachers often lack the training to design quality assessment tasks and even if they are well trained, they often lack the time due to “heavy work load” as claimed (Mayotte, 2011; Reyneke, Meyer & Nel, 2010). There seems to be laxity on the part of teachers as well. Internal assessment has been subjected to a great deal of abuse and misinterpretations by teachers because most of them appear not to understand the rationale for internal assessment in the school secondary system.

Most teachers lack skills in test construction and administration, and their attitudes toward the internal assessment approach and record keeping are negative (Alausa, 2000). Large class sizes in most secondary schools and particularly public schools and the increase in the workload are challenges advanced to excuse the teachers (Kapambwe, 2010). The teacher’s literacy level and commitment towards internal assessment is vital for effective implementation. The teachers’ knowledge of internal assessment has a direct effect, teachers’ perception towards internal assessment and teachers’ attitude towards internal assessment have an indirect effect on its implementation (Olufemi, Kassim, and Olufunbi, 2011). Furthermore, some teachers also inflate pupils’ scores, which have a negative effect on the weighting and this makes it difficult to compare such internal assessment scores and those from central examination bodies.

Nxumalo (2007) indicated that the teachers did not attend any training to conduct and implement internal assessment in their classroom. Lacks of training are barriers to implementing internal assessment for supporting lower achievers to improve (Hayford, 2007). The lack of training results to testing tasks that are always substandard. For lack of skills in test development, the teacher will always lift questions from old question papers not minding whether they reflect and cover the content. Objectives and levels of objectives to test are not considered in developing testing tasks. The untrained teacher does not understand the principles of testing. He sees testing as tricking the testee hence predictive validity may fail in his test items.

Lack of training leads in most cases, to the testing environment being harsh, intimidating and frustrating. Instead of establishing rapport with testee, the teacher would want to be a monster to be feared by the testee. This is because he does not understand the psychology of the testee and the principle behind testing. To the untrained teacher, arrangement of testing material and environment is the responsibility of the test taker hence the control of invalidation is ignored by the untrained teacher.

Finally, a system of moderation of teachers’ judgments through professional collaboration benefits teaching and learning as well as assessment. Moderation that affects the planning and implementation of assessment, and consequently teachers’ understanding of learning goals and of the criteria indicating progress towards them, has more than a quality assurance function.

The provision of a bank of well-designed tasks, with marking criteria, can do more than help teachers to make judgments about their pupils’ achievements. Such tasks exemplify activities through which pupils can work towards important goals, such as critical reasoning and the application of knowledge in new situations. As assessment tasks they can provide pupils with interesting and relevant learning experiences. They should not be allowed to dominate the assessment process and certainly should not be seen as separate measures to be set beside teachers’ judgments. Nor are they intended to confirm teachers’ judgments. Rather they are part of the

evidence that teachers can use, if needed, to ensure that all intended goals are taken into account in their assessment.

Summary of Implications for teachers

Ensure that assessment is always used to help learning and that, when a summative assessment report is needed, the best evidence is reliably judged against relevant criteria.

Involve pupils in self-assessment of ongoing work and help them to understand the criteria used in assessing their work for reporting purposes and how summative judgments are made.

Take part in moderation of summative judgments and other quality assurance procedures.

Use tests only when most appropriate, not as routine.

CONCLUSION

Internal assessment calls for change of attitude of many teachers who were used to old traditional way of assessment. Also, teachers must attempt to pursue refresher courses and re-training on their own for their personal growth (Nxumalo, 2007). As internal assessment strategies are not yet frequently used by teachers' research should focus on designing, developing, and implementing professional development interventions to stimulate teachers' use of internal assessment strategies further.

SUGGESTIONS

When all these are applied by the teachers, it will not only build confidence in their student but will also help reduce the dreaded hydra headed monster of examination malpractices in our school system. Every individual aspiring to teach must have a basic teacher training. He should be exposed to educational psychology alongside with his field of study. Basic teaching methods as well as learning theories should be exposed to him. More importantly with the current spate of examination malpractices and leakages, every individual aspiring to teach or is already teaching, should be given basic knowledge of measurement and evaluation whereby he will be exposed to skill of test preparation and testing. Government and educational agencies should organize in-service trainings, workshop and seminars to get teachers exposed to and acquainted with the current technicalities of testing. Examination committee should be established in schools, whose members must have requisite knowledge of testing. The Ministry of Education should provide training for teachers to construct their own assessment tasks since, without this training, teachers might resort to developing items that assess only low-level cognitive skills Mchazime (2003).

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